

Data Management Plan

MAP-IT-NOW Project for Algal Bloom Monitoring and Visualization

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NSF Division: OCE

This project aims to predict algal blooms along the Mid-atlantic U. S. Coast by developing an algorithm that correlates novel ecological data with climate and geographic data. Data will be collected from NASA Earth observation archives, active acquisition from current orbiting platforms and field and lab work. These data will include geochemical, geophysical, molecular, ecological, and observational analysis. Data will be stored in the format that conforms with the BCO-DMO standard. During the study, project data will be stored locally at the laboratory of Dr. Cher and her Co-PIs, and also backed up using UIUC IT services. There are no personal information/privacy risks as part of this study.

Product 1: Oceanographic Data

Cher, R.E.

Metadata and assessments from environmental samples

Creation Plan: Water samples will be collected from different points along the shoreline coast from New Jersey to Georgia, such as the estuaries, interconnected waterways, barrier islands and near shore environments. Standard environmental data will be collected at all time points to provide comparisons between sampling trips. While water samples will be discarded at the conclusion of the study, key metadata collected from the samples will be archived. Ecological species assessment data will be collected from coastal area to determine changes in populations size or structure. These assessments will require the collection of biogeochemical parameters to better understand the system-level shifts predicted.

Anticipated Volume: 1-5 GB data

Format(s): standard BCO-DMO project metadata forms (.rtf)

Intended Repository: BCO-DMO

Release Timeline: immediate

Product 2: GeoBiology Data

Smith, J.A.

Genetic sequences obtained from environmental samples

Creation Plan: Taxa will be assigned using the RDP Bayesian rRNA Classifier (Wang et al., 2007) and Silva for Bacteria and fungi sequences and verified through the BLAST database.

Anticipated Volume: <1 GB

Format(s): .fasta sequences

Intended Repository: GenBank

Release Timeline: immediate

Product 3: Geochemical/Geochronological Software

Hancock, J.A.

novel MAP-IT-NOW software to visualize sample and condition data in correlation with presence of algal blooms and environmental disasters over time.

Anticipated Volume: 200 MB

Format(s): Python 3.0

Intended Repository: Github

Release Timeline: immediate

Product 4: Interdisciplinary Curriculum

Hancock, J.A.

MAP-IT-NOW Visualization tool website for educational and outreach purposes

Creation Plan: We will create a user interface for students and faculty to access our data and share within the classroom.

Format(s): JSP

Intended Repository: Laboratory website, tbd

Release Timeline: immediate

Product 5: Oceanographic Specimen *Cher, R.E.*

no specimens will be kept/ physically archived as part of this study

Preservation Plan:

Metadata Release Timeline: